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E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Connecting Visions: from shared strategies to regional transformation

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We connect
various actors
and break down
barriers

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators

Deliverable 2.1 Results

Mapping the Research and Innovation Landscape: Key Findings from WP2 Tasks 2.1 and 2.2

The report ENTRN DEL 2.1.01/2023 offers an in-depth analysis of the Research and Innovation (R&I) landscape of the E³UDRES² alliance, reflecting progress after two years of collaboration. It summarises the work carried out under Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 of Work Package 2, and presents key findings on research topics, institutional expertise, and collaboration mechanisms across the alliance.

Strategic Alignment and Thematic Priorities

The analysis confirms that the alliance's research activities are well aligned with major European policy priorities and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). A significant portion of the reviewed literature supports the relevance of the alliance's focus areas.

- The initial three research networks – Wellbeing and Active-Ageing, Circular Economy, and Human Contribution to AI – reflect the interdisciplinary strengths of the partner institutions. Among these, Circular Economy appears in approximately 73% of the analysed literature, followed by Wellbeing and Active Ageing (~53%) and Human Contribution to AI (~33%).
- In preparation for the next phase (E³UDRES² 2.0), the alliance identified four new priority areas: Health, Wellbeing and Social Inclusion for Regions; Digital Solutions and (Applied) Deep Tech for Regions; Resilient Economy and Innovation for Regions; and Creative Industries for Regions' Identity. The topic Resilient Economy and Innovation for Regions is the most frequent in the literature (~73%).

- The six Open Innovation Hubs developed under the E.I.N.S. project were grounded in regional challenge mapping. Among these hubs, the topic Food was the most represented in the reviewed publications (~67%).

While the alignment with policy priorities is strong, the report also identifies gaps in expertise. Some key EU mission topics – such as cancer research or communicable diseases – are not currently represented in the alliance's work due to limited medical research capacity. Other underrepresented themes include renewable energy, low-carbon technologies, precision medicine, and material resource efficiency.

Expertise and Engagement

The alliance brings together researchers from a broad spectrum of disciplines across six institutions – including Universities of Applied Sciences and research universities – covering fields such as Engineering, Life Sciences, Business, Social Sciences, and Design.

- A total of 164 researchers were formally registered across the three networks at the time of analysis. The Wellbeing and Active-Ageing network involved 84 researchers (47%), Circular Economy 62 (34%), and Human Contribution to AI 34 (19%). The lower engagement in AI-related research is identified as a strategic challenge.

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators

Deliverable 2.1 Results

Expertise and Engagement (cont.)

- A bibliometric analysis using SciVal and Scopus data showed strong representation in Engineering (29.5%), Agricultural and Biological Sciences (22.4%), Computer Science (18.6%), and Environmental Science (15.7%). This suggests potential for interdisciplinary cooperation. However, the report notes that Scopus coverage is incomplete and recommends closer collaboration with HR and R&D units to build an internal research mapping system.

Research Collaboration

A key strength of E³UDRES² is its commitment to cross-institutional and interdisciplinary collaboration.

- Initiatives such as Research I-living Labs (two editions held), Markets of Researchers, and joint project submissions have supported collaboration across institutions and disciplines.
- Research networks have submitted proposals to programmes such as Horizon Europe and ERA-Net. At the time of reporting, the Accelerate_FutureHEI project (HORIZON-WIDERA) had been approved, while other proposals were still under evaluation.
- Engagement with regional stakeholders is integrated into many R&I activities. Events such as the Market of Stakeholders and regional stakeholder workshops have facilitated dialogue between researchers and societal actors across partner countries.

SWOT Analysis

The report includes a SWOT analysis that highlights the alliance's strengths, such as its alignment with EU policy, interdisciplinary scope, and various stakeholder engagement formats. Challenges include the lack of a formalised R&I strategy, low researcher engagement, and limited experience in shared infrastructure and joint publishing. Nonetheless, opportunities such as digitalisation, societal interest in sustainability, and EU-level R&I support offer promising pathways forward.

Follow the link to read the full deliverable: [Deliverable 2.1 Mapping the Research and Innovation Landscape: Key Findings from WP2 Tasks 2.1 and 2.2.](#)

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators

Deliverable 4.2: Developing a Training Curricula to Provide OS/OI/OE/OA Skills and Competencies

In this newsletter edition we will focus on the Deliverable 4.2 “Ent-r-e-novators SWOT analysis of training offers/needs in OS/OI/OE/OA (Open Science, Open Innovatio, Open Education, Open Aceso) and Development of a training curricula for providing OS/OI/OE/OA skills and competences” results, which you can find on our [website](#).

The Ent-r-e-novators WP4 team developed an Open Practices Joint Training Curricula with the aim to enable Higher Education stakeholders, to empower learners with the ability to leverage open practices, share knowledge, collaborate across disciplines, and drive innovation in their respective fields.

Through this joint training program, academia gains a comprehensive understanding of the principles and practices of OE/OA/OS/OI, equipping them with the tools and mindset required to engage in open research, develop open educational resources, foster a culture of transparency and collaboration in academia, and actively contribute to the innovation ecosystem.

With this training, university stakeholders in our institutions and beyond will receive a unique opportunity to grow towards becoming an Open Practices designer, developer and integrator in formal education and research. Based on an extensive analysis of several resources, regulations and policies we defined several competencies needed for Open Practices.

To identify a course competencies, we consider the Domains of Learning: knowledge, skills, and attitudes. These competencies will help identify the general facts and principles (knowledge), procedures and methods (skills), and values and characteristics (attitudes) that learners will attain from the OE/OA/OS/OI Joint Training Curricula.

The OE/OA/OS/OI Joint Training Curricula are mostly common and include Licensing Knowledge, Research Skills, collaboration and co-creation, advocacy, ethics and integrity, and others.

Developing competencies in these areas can lead to more effective participation in open practices, ultimately contributing to the broader goals of transparency, collaboration, and accessibility in education, research, and innovation.

This Joint Training Curricula, over 100 different courses and modules will be integrated as OERs, supplementary readings or full courses, as part of the the joint training curricula.

The Open Education, Open Access, Open Science, and Open Innovation independent courses will incorporate and indicate resources in the languages of each of the partners. Open educational resources as a collection of readings, videos, and online resources will be provided for each week.

Follow the link to read the full deliverable: [Deliverable 4.2 Open report on 3-level \(institutional, national and international\) scenario & risk analysis.](#)

21 JULY 2025

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Video Series Gabriele Permoser WP2 Overview

As part of the Ent-r-e-novators video series, Gabriele Permoser, WP2 Lead, presents a detailed reflection on the work carried out under Work Package 2 (WP2), dedicated to the development of the Joint Research and Innovation Agenda (JRIA) for the E³UDRES² European University Alliance.

WP2 adopted a participatory, evidence-based methodology aimed at ensuring that the agenda reflected both the diversity of regional contexts and the strategic direction of the European Research Area. A range of activities was carried out, including surveys, interviews and focus groups, engaging students, academic staff, researchers, citizens and regional stakeholders. This inclusive approach made it possible to gather valuable insights, expectations and ideas from those directly involved in and affected by research and innovation processes.

In parallel, the WP2 team conducted an extensive review of relevant European policy frameworks in research, innovation and higher education. This ensured that the JRIA was not only grounded in the realities of the E³UDRES² institutions and regions, but also aligned with the broader priorities and objectives defined at European level.

The resulting “Joint Research and Innovation Agenda” defines common priorities and strategic pillars that will guide future collaborative research efforts across the alliance. It is designed as a living, adaptable document that can support transdisciplinary approaches, societal relevance, and long-term impact. It reinforces E³UDRES²'s ambition to contribute meaningfully to regional development, sustainability and knowledge co-creation. The next step will be the joint approval of the agenda by all partner institutions, paving the way for its practical implementation and integration into institutional research strategies.

[Check the video on our youtube channel](#)

26 SEPTEMBER 2025

Save the Date: Ent-r-e-novators will take part in the European Researchers' Night 2025

On 26 September 2025, the European Researchers' Night will once again bring science closer to society, with activities taking place in more than 400 cities across Europe and beyond. The Ent-r-e-novators project will be part of this major European event that celebrates the impact of research on our daily lives. Organised annually, the event aims to promote science and innovation, particularly among younger audiences, through interactive activities, exhibitions, and conversations with researchers.

The Ent-r-e-novators project will be present at the event across multiple partner institutions, contributing to local programmes with activities that highlight the project's commitment to open, engaged, and inclusive science in smart and sustainable regions. More information will be shared soon.

13 MAY 2025

Thematic Corners: VALORIZA project at the Science Policy Conference

As part of the Thematic Corners of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Science Policy Conference, held on 13 May 2025, the VALORIZA R&D Unit (IPPortalegre) was represented by Paulo Brito. The session highlighted applied research projects that are driving smart and sustainable regional development.

The presentation focused on the work developed by VALORIZA – Research Centre for the Valorisation of Endogenous Resources, a centre dedicated to territorial development through science and innovation.

Its mission is to explore and apply information technologies to optimise the use of waste resources, including agricultural, forestry, and municipal solid waste, in ways that support economic and social value creation. An example highlighted during the session was the VALORBIO project, which investigates the potential of biorefineries based on residual materials, aiming to generate high-value products while contributing to sustainability goals. VALORIZA's approach is not only focused on resource efficiency but also on regional growth, entrepreneurship, and the stimulation of innovation ecosystems. The project's video presentation is available on the Ent-r-e-novators [YouTube channel](#) and on the official project website.

13 MAY 2025

Thematic Corners: Energy transition project at the Ent-r-e-novators Science Policy Conference

As part of the Science Policy Conference, the EnergyTran project was featured in the Thematic Corner, fostering critical dialogue around the role of international cooperation and citizen science in enabling a fair and sustainable energy transition. The initiative was highlighted for its capacity to connect applied research with civic engagement and multistakeholder collaboration. Two short video testimonies were recorded at the Thematic Corner during the conference, providing first-hand insights from project participants:– Jazmín Calderón Queirós, a biologist at CeNAT-CONARE (Costa Rica), actively contributes to the EnergyTran initiative. With a background in environmental science, she works on strengthening Costa Rica's scientific ecosystem and promoting regional collaboration in sustainable energy.– Giriane Rocha, a master's student in environmental management and research fellow at the Polytechnic University of Setúbal (Portugal), participates in the EnergyTran project through a research grant focused on citizen science and science-policy interfaces. Jazmín Calderón Queirós emphasized the importance of open science and international collaboration to develop technological solutions with social and environmental applicability. She highlighted Costa Rica's challenges in maintaining energy efficiency and the relevance of EnergyTran in strengthening research capacities and improving communication channels for sustainable development. Giriane Rocha focused on the project's collective dimension, underlining the creation of a transnational knowledge community. She reflected on the value of academic mobility, the participation of over 300 people in project activities, and the role of EnergyTran in fostering capacity building through hands-on experiences and hybrid learning environments. The project's visibility in this policy context reinforces its potential as a scalable model for bi-regional cooperation between the EU and Latin America, bringing together research, higher education and society in the co-design of innovative solutions for a just energy transition.

Giriane Rocha

Jazmín Calderón Queirós

Watch their reflections and discover how EnergyTran is helping reshape the role of research in society: [Giriane Rocha](#) and [Jasmin](#).

13 MAY 2025

Thematic Corners: Ent-r-e-novators project at the Science Policy Conference

The Thematic Corner of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project stood out as a vibrant space for dialogue, collaboration, and visibility at the E³UDRES² Science Policy Conference. Designed to connect interdisciplinary research with regional innovation ecosystems, this thematic corner served as a bridge between academic institutions, policymakers, research infrastructures, and fellow European initiatives.

Like to know more? Dive into the full experience and discover how the Ent-r-e-novators project is shaping the future of research and innovation in Europe. Watch the highlights on our [YouTube](#) channel and explore more at entrenovators.eu.

Launched in October 2022 and funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe Programme, the Ent-r-e-novators project is a 36-month initiative managed by the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Its mission is to strengthen the research and innovation capacity of higher education institutions and their surrounding ecosystems, fostering scientific excellence, research integrity, and collaborative methods across sectors and disciplines.

This thematic corner presented the project's core vision: a deep diagnostic of existing research and innovation assets across Europe—covering infrastructures, human resources, research activities, Open Science practices, and societal engagement. It also promoted the development of future-facing R&I competencies and tools that empower universities to collaborate more effectively with local stakeholders.

Participants at the event explored how Ent-r-e-novators contributes to regional transformation by building smart and sustainable research networks.

The corner also facilitated exchange with other relevant projects and research centers such as EnergyTran, MARE, Citizen Science (KU Leuven), and Valoriza, reinforcing the synergies between them and the Ent-r-e-novators project and the European University E3UDRES2 alliance..

13 MAY 2025

Energytran project: A year working on fostering science cooperation between Europe and Latin -America to achieve a fair and sustainable energy transition, are we close?

Six month ago, we presented the cluster project [Energytran](#) on our [Newsletter 4^o edition](#), as a good practice to deal with the challenge of energy transition. We introduced the strategies lines implemented on the project to do it focused not only on technological development, but also on social impact of the energy transition, its environmental impact and also the transfer of the knowledge generated by the research cooperation to policy makers. It is not easy to work by this way, but Energytran consortium think that is the only one to generate really a green, fair and equal energy transition.

In addition, on that article the Energytran Consortium was introduced as a complex and multisectoral teams that also we consider essential to tackle the multidisciplinary goal of the decarbonization: 11 partners (now we are 12 because UMAG was incorporated an associated partner from Chile). Concretely, we are two European Research Infrastructures Consortium - ERIC- (one for Energy and other for Environment) that involved 18 institutions from Spain, France, Germany, Cyprus, Portugal and Greece (in the case of Eu-Solaris ERIC) and 8 from Belgium, Bulgaria, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain (in the case of LifeWatch ERIC); 8 public research centres and universities (3 from Europe -IPS, INESC TEC from Portugal and CSIC from Spain- and 5 from Latin-America and the Caribbean (LAC) -TECNM from Mexico, UNNE and UNSAM from Argentina, PUC from Chile and CENAT from Costa Rica-) and finally, the International Organization OEI (Organization of Ibero American States for Education, Science and Culture) that involves 23 governments (20 Latin American ones, Portugal, Spain and Andorra). Consequently, that is 58 entities working directly or indirectly together from 32 countries (20 from LAC and 12 from Europe).

13 MAY 2025

Energytran project: A year working on fostering science cooperation between Europe and Latin America to achieve a fair and sustainable energy transition, are we close?

To make this project possible, we have developed four principles in order to transfer this approach on a methodology. On one hand, “horizontal cooperation”. Energytran project put particular attention on international cooperation but considering that all of partners are at the same level. Secondly, “inclusiveness”. We think that it is necessary to integrate inclusive dimension in energy transition (gender, indigenous perspective, etc.) in order to get a fair and equal energy transition. The third dimension of this scientific cooperation is the “participative methodologies”: different stakeholders should be involved on energy transition, not only researchers but also policy makers, enterprises and civil society. And finally, “social relevant impact”. The objective of this principle is to highlight that any Research and Innovation initiative should have social impact and service to public policies and society.

From the beginning of the project in January 2024 until now, more than 300 people (mostly researchers and technicians from public bodies) have been involved on the Energytran activities such as virtual thematic events, international or national workshops and mobilities. In this sense, mobilities have been one of the most relevant actions to promote knowledge exchange and scientific cooperation networks between LAC and Europe. As one researcher said, “I could learn more about a new technology that I could later implement in a local community which we work with in my university”. Actually, 30 mobilities have been considered on Energytran project from ALC to Europe and 15 from Europe to ALC.

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13 MAY 2025

Energytran project: A year working on fostering science cooperation between Europe and Latin America to achieve a fair and sustainable energy transition, are we close? -

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In this point, it is important to highlight the interest of European Research Infrastructures in the cooperation with Latin American in the field of energy transition. In Energytran we launched a call for expression of interest in Europe to host mobilities from Latin-American research centers and we received almost 40 expressions of interest from Spain, Portugal, France, Germany and Cyprus. We couldn't cover all of them, so this is still necessary to support this kind of cooperation.

For Energytran Consortium the dissemination and exploitation of the project results is so relevant. We have already participated in 16 external events (e.g. [Foro CILAC](#)), developed 10 papers or articles (available in Energytran website) and published more than 120 news in social networks. Furthermore, it is important to highlight that there are already a lot of initiatives in Europe and LAC focused on promoting energy transition.

Some of those initiatives emerge from top to down, for instance, public initiatives with significant social and productive impact (that is the case of the Solar Energy Program for SMEs and the Photovoltaic Plant on the wholesale market of Mexico City, that is the biggest on an urban area with 30 thousand solar panels installed). Others emerge from the scientific sector through knowledge co-generation processes with local communities (that is the case of UNNE with QOM community in Argentina); and others from self-managed communities where consumers and producers work together, even creating a pro-consumer role (that is the case of the wind system in Costa Rica).

Consequently in Energytran we want also to show initiatives from both regions to learn each other about how to decarbonize the energy matrix, how to integrate local communities into technological development through participatory processes, on how to combine sovereignty, sustainability, equal access and economic value.

As a conclusion Energytran is contributing to establish long-term partnerships between European and Latin American and Caribbean (LAC) research institutions. In addition, we are exchanging knowledge and best practices in energy transition through generating and transferring knowledge to policymakers and other stakeholders of the landscape.

13 MAY 2025

Energytran project: A year working on fostering science cooperation between Europe and Latin -America to achieve a fair and sustainable energy transition, are we close?

Energytran is also facilitating spaces for cooperation, such as mobility and the Network4collaboration Platform and fostering the capacities of main stakeholders on scientific cooperation about how to integrate open science and sustainability on energy transition and, finally, we are developing and testing new tools for the analysis of the impacts of the energy transition on SDGs and the contribution of science on that field.

The transition toward fairer and more sustainable socioeconomic models requires depth transformations in basic systems such as energy. Energytran is an initiative of scientific cooperation between Europe and Latin-American and the Caribbean countries providing some outputs that will contribute to solving this global and complex problem. We are not close to the solution, but we are on the right way.

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